

1 **SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES**

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4 **Figure S1. C4 from TYLCV must be at the plasma membrane to trigger developmental**
5 **alterations in tomato plants.**

6 Developmental phenotype of transgenic tomato plants expressing C4 and C4_{G2A} under a 35S
7 promoter in the T1 generation. Images were taken at 60 days post-germination. Scale bar, 2
8 cm.

9 C4, C4 from TYLCV; EV, empty vector.

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11 **Figure S2. C4 from TYLCV interacts with RLD proteins, of which the coding genes are**
 12 **expressed in the vasculature.**

13 a. Interaction between C4 and NbSK η , tested by yeast two-hybrid (Y2H). The NbSK η construct
 14 is from Mei *et al.*, 2018b.

15 b. Interaction between C4 and the BRX domain of Arabidopsis RLD1-4 (BRXD) tested by Y2H.

16 c. Interaction between C4 and full-length Arabidopsis RLD1-4 tested by Y2H.

17 d. Interaction between C4 and full-length tomato RLD1 and 2 (SIRLD1/2) or their BRX domains
 18 (BRXD).

19 e. Histochemical GUS staining of RLD1/RLD2/RLD3/RLD4 promoter:GUS transgenic
 20 Arabidopsis lines (T5 generation). Images were taken 3 days after germination using a Zeiss
 21 Imager M2 microscope. Three independent single-copy transgenic lines were tested per
 22 construct with similar results. Scale bar, 100 μ m.

23 The experiments in a, b, c and d were performed three times with similar results. One replicate
 24 is shown here.

25 C4, C4 from TYLCV.

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27 **Figure S3. C4 outcompetes LZY and recruits RLD proteins to the plasma membrane.**

28 a, b. Subcellular localization of RFP-RLD1, 2, and 4 transiently expressed in *N. benthamiana*
 29 leaves in the presence (a) or absence (b) of C4-GFP. White rectangles indicate close-ups.
 30 Images were taken at 2 days post-agroinfiltration (dpa).

31 c. Interaction between LZY3 (LZY3-YN) and RLD1, 2, and 4 (RLD1/2/4-YC) as detected by
 32 bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC) upon transient expression in *N.*
 33 *benthamiana* leaves with or without C4. Images were taken at 2 dpa. Laser intensity was kept
 34 equal during image acquisition for all samples.

35 d. YFP intensity of the samples in (c), quantified using ImageJ. Each dot represents the YFP
 36 intensity value obtained for one technical replicate consisting of one field; lines represent the
 37 average value per sample. A minimum of six fields were analyzed per combination; asterisks
 38 indicate a statistically significant difference according to Student's t test (***, $P < 0.001$). Images
 39 were taken at 2 dpa. BF, bright field.

40 Z-stack shows the maximum projection of a vertical cross-section through the observed cells.
41 Scale bar, 20 μm . The experiments in a, b and c were performed three times with similar
42 results. One replicate is shown here.
43 C4, C4 from TYLCV.
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47 a, b. Alignments between the C4 protein sequence from TYLCV and that from 16 selected
48 monopartite begomoviruses causing tomato leaf curl disease (a), or that from 7 selected
49 bipartite begomoviruses (b). In (b), TYLCV is shown for reference.

50 c. Alignment between C4 protein sequence from BSCTV (belonging to the *Curtovirus* genus),
51 TLCYnV (which interacts with NbSK η), TYLCV-Mild, and TYLCV.

52 Multiple sequence alignments were performed by BioEdit software. The CCL-like sequence is
53 framed in a black rectangle. All sequences were downloaded from GenBank; details regarding
54 virus species, isolate, and accession numbers can be found in Table S7.

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57 **Figure S5. The inclusion of a CCL-like domain in the CCL-like-free C4 from TYLCV-Mild**
 58 **is not sufficient to promote its interaction with RLDs.**

59 a. Design of C4 Mild_m. Key amino acids of the CCL-like domain of C4, highlighted in red bold
 60 letters, were introduced at equivalent positions in C4 Mild, generating C4 Mild_m, now
 61 containing a CCL-like domain. Numbers indicate amino acid positions in the corresponding
 62 proteins.

63 b. Interaction between C4 Mild and the BRX domain (BRXD) of Arabidopsis RLD1-4, tested
 64 by yeast two-hybrid (Y2H).

65 c. Interaction between C4 Mild and full-length Arabidopsis RLD1-4, tested by Y2H.

66 d. Interaction between C4 Mild_m and the BRX domain (BRXD) of Arabidopsis RLD1-4, tested
 67 by Y2H.

68 e. Interaction between C4 Mild_m and full-length Arabidopsis RLD1-4, tested by Y2H.

69 These experiments were performed three times with similar results; one representative
 70 replicate is shown here.

71 C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild; C4, C4 from TYLCV.

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74 **Figure S6. C4_{CCLm1} and C4_{CCLm2} do not interact with RLD proteins.**

75 a. Interaction between C4_{CCLm1}/C4_{CCLm2} and the BRX domain (BRXD) of Arabidopsis RLD1-4,
76 tested by yeast two-hybrid (Y2H).

77 b. Interaction between C4_{CCLm1} and full-length Arabidopsis RLD1-4, tested by Y2H.

78 c. Interaction between C4_{CCLm2} and full-length RLD1-4, tested by Y2H.

79 d. Interaction between C4_{CCLm1} and RLD3 upon transient co-expression in *N. benthamiana*
80 leaves, analyzed by FRET-FLIM. FE, FRET efficiency. The membrane protein IAN9 is used
81 as negative control. Samples were taken at 2 days post-agroinfiltration. Each dot represents
82 the GFP fluorescence lifetime (ns, nanoseconds) of one technical replicate consisting of one
83 field; the thick line indicates the average value, and the error bars correspond to standard
84 deviations. Significant differences between groups were determined by one-way ANOVA
85 ($P < 0.0001$, $F = 80.63$, $df = 3$), followed by multiple comparisons of means by applying Tukey test;
86 asterisks represent statistically significant differences at: ****, $P < 0.0001$; ns, not significant.

87 All experiments in this figure were performed three times with similar results. One replicate is
88 shown.

89 C4, C4 from TYLCV.

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92 **Figure S7. An intact CCL-like domain is required for C4 from TYLCV to interact with**
 93 **RLDs, but dispensable for other interactions of C4 at the plasma membrane.**

94 a. Subcellular localization of Arabidopsis RFP-RLD1, 2, and 4 transiently expressed in *N.*
 95 *benthamiana* leaves in the presence or absence of $C4_{\text{CCLm1}}$ / $C4_{\text{CCLm2}}$ -GFP. White rectangles
 96 indicate close-ups.

97 b. Subcellular localization of C4-GFP/ $C4_{\text{CCLm1}}$ -GFP/ $C4_{\text{CCLm2}}$ -GFP upon transient expression in
 98 *N. benthamiana* leaves. Aniline blue staining labels callose deposits. Arrowheads indicate
 99 plasmodesmata.

100 In a,b, Images were taken at 2 days post-agroinfiltration. BF, bright field. Z-stack shows the
101 maximum projection of a vertical cross-section through the observed cells. Scale bar, 20 μ m.

102 c. Interaction between full-length tomato RLD1 and 2 (SIRLD1/2) and C4_{CCLm1}/C4_{CCLm2}/C4 Mild,
103 tested by yeast two-hybrid (Y2H).

104 d. Interaction between the BRX domain (BRXD) of SIRLD1/SIRLD2 and C4_{CCLm1}/C4_{CCLm2}/C4
105 Mild/C4 Mild_m, tested by Y2H.

106 e. Interaction between the kinase domain (678-1003aa) of the plasma membrane-localized
107 receptor kinase BAM1 and C4/C4_{CCLm1}/C4_{CCLm2}/C4 Mild/C4 Mild_m, tested by Y2H.

108 All experiments were performed three times with similar results; one representative replicate
109 is shown here.

110 C4, C4 from TYLCV, C4 Mild, C4 Mild from TYLCV-Mild

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113 **Figure S8. Bleaching spread and transgene expression in SUC:SUL Arabidopsis plants**
 114 **transformed with C4 variants.**

115 a. Representative images of bleaching spread phenotype in leaves of 4-week-old SUC:SUL
 116 (S-S) plants expressing C4, C4 Mild, or their respective mutant forms (T2 generation). Scale
 117 bar, 1 cm. S-S/EV as well as non-transformed S-S leaves are shown as controls.

118 b. Expression levels of C4 variants (WT and mutants) in the transgenic plants shown in (a),
 119 measured by RT-qPCR. Note that reference level (set to 1) for C4 variants is C4 WT (averaged
 120 L8+L22, T3), whereas for C4 Mild variants is C4 Mild WT (averaged L28, T3).

121 c. Expression level of the *SUL-ChSA* (chalcone synthase intron) construct from the transgenic
 122 SUC:SUL cassette, in the transgenic plants shown in (a), by RT-qPCR. Note that reference
 123 level (set to 1) corresponds to S-S/EV (average L1+L6).

124 d. Expression levels of the endogenous *SUL* gene in the transgenic plants shown in (a),
 125 measured by RT-qPCR. Note that reference level (set to 1) corresponds to WT.

126 In the graphs in b, c, d, each bar represents the value obtained per individual RNA sample,
127 consisting of a pool of material coming from four different plants.
128 C4, C4 from TYLCV; C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild; S-S, SUC:SUL plants; EV, empty vector.
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131 **Figure S9. Developmental phenotypes and transgene expression in Arabidopsis plants**
 132 **transformed with C4 variants.**

133 a, b. Representative phenotypes in rosettes of 34-days-old plants (a) and in stems, siliques,
 134 and inflorescences of 59-days-old plants (b) expressing C4, C4 Mild, or their respective mutant
 135 forms (T3 generation). Scale bar in (a), 2 cm; scale bar in (b), 4 cm.

136 c. Relative expression levels of the C4 variants in the transgenic plants shown in (a), measured
 137 by RT-qPCR. Note that reference level (set to 1) for C4 variants is 35S:C4 (L22, T3), whereas
 138 for C4 Mild variants is 35S:C4 Mild (L7, T3). A stable line expressing GFP (35S:GFP) is shown
 139 as reference and as negative control in expression analyses. Note that the plants used in (b)
 140 as reference (35S:GFP as well as 35S:C4 lines) are the same in different pictures.

141 C4, C4 from TYLCV; C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild; dpg, days post-germination.

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Figure S10. Root phenotypes in Arabidopsis plants transformed with C4 variants.

145 a. Representative root phenotypes in plants expressing C4, C4 Mild, or their respective mutant
 146 forms (T3 generation), at 14 days post-germination. Scale bar, 1 cm. A stable line expressing
 147 GFP (35S:GFP) is shown as reference. Note that some pictures in (a) are also included in
 148 Figure S12a as reference, since both experiments were run in parallel.

149 b, c. Quantifications of the primary root length (b) and of the number of lateral roots per unit of
 150 primary root length (c), as obtained in three independent experiments. In (b), each dot
 151 represents the root length of an individual plant, and the error bars indicate standard deviations;
 152 a minimum of 6 plants were analyzed per line. Significant differences between groups were
 153 determined by either one-way ANOVA (middle graph, $P=2.19E-10$, $F=11.044$, $df=10$) or
 154 Kruskal-Wallis (upper graph, $P=2,029E-14$, $H=87.078$, $df=10$; bottom graph, $P=5.73E-10$,
 155 $H=64.213$, $df=10$), followed by multiple comparisons of means between the C4-expressing
 156 lines against the reference group (35S:GFP), by applying either Dunnett's test (middle graph)
 157 or pairwise comparisons between each group and the reference group (upper and bottom

158 graphs, Mann-Whitney U test, significance 0.005, after Bonferroni's correction for multiple
159 comparisons); asterisks represent statistically significant differences at: ***, $P < 0.001$; **, $P < 0.01$;
160 $P < 0.01$; ns, not significant. In (c), each dot represents the number of lateral roots per unit of
161 primary root length of an individual plant, and the error bars the lowest/highest values; a
162 minimum of 6 plants were analyzed per line. Significant differences between groups were
163 determined by one-way ANOVA (upper graph, $P = 5.70E-10$, $F = 9.298$, $df = 10$; middle graph,
164 $P = 1.14E-8$, $F = 8.778$, $df = 10$; bottom graph, $P = 1.92E-17$, $F = 15.487$, $df = 10$), followed by
165 multiple comparisons of means between the C4-expressing lines against the reference group
166 (35S:GFP), by applying Dunnett's test; asterisks represent statistically significant differences
167 at: ***, $P < 0.001$; **, $P < 0.01$; ns, not significant.

168 C4, C4 from TYLCV; C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild.

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171 **Figure S11. Overexpression of *RLD3* alleviates C4-induced developmental phenotypes**
 172 **in Arabidopsis.**

173 a. Representative rosette phenotypes in the F1 generation plants resulting from crossing
 174 35S:C4 lines 8 and 22 (T2) with 35S:AtRLD3 lines 20 and 10 (T2) parentals, respectively, at
 175 35 days post-germination (dpg) (upper panel, on the left) or at 65 dpg (middle panel); scale
 176 bar, 2 cm. Complete plants (bottom panels) were also photographed at 65 dpg; scale bar, 5
 177 cm. In these experiments, F1s coming from crossing a stable line expressing GFP (35S:GFP)
 178 with 35S:AtRLD3 T2 parentals or with itself are used as controls. The bar graph (upper panel,
 179 on the right) shows the quantification of the rosette average radius at 35 dpg; each dot
 180 represents the average of three radius measurements per rosette, and error bars indicate
 181 standard deviations. A minimum of 11 rosettes per genotype were analyzed, when possible.
 182 Differences between pairs of groups were assessed by applying Mann-Whitney U test;
 183 asterisks represent statistically significant differences at: ***, $P < 0.001$; **, $P < 0.01$; ns, not
 184 significant.

185 b. Relative expression levels of *AtRLD3* and *C4* in the plants shown in (a), measured by RT-
186 qPCR. Note that reference level (set to 1) for *AtRLD3* is F1 35S:GFP x 35S:GFP, whereas for
187 *C4* is 35S:C4 (averaged L8+22, T3).

188 C4, C4 from TYLCV; dpg, days post-germination.

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191 **Figure S12. Root gravitropic responses are altered in Arabidopsis plants expressing C4**
 192 **from TYLCV.**

193 a. Pictures show representative root phenotypes in plants expressing C4, C4 Mild, or their
 194 respective mutant forms (T3 generation), at 14 days post-germination (dpg). Scale bar, 1 cm.
 195 A stable line expressing GFP (35S:GFP) is shown as reference. Graphs show quantifications
 196 of the lateral root angles relative to the main roots in the previous transgenic plants (gravitropic
 197 set-point angles, GSAs), in two independent experiments. Each dot represents the angle
 198 measurements of a lateral root, and error bars indicate standard deviations. Angles of four
 199 different roots per plant were measured, and a minimum of 6 plants were analyzed per line.
 200 Significant differences between groups were determined by one-way ANOVA (replicate on the
 201 left: $P=2.77E-26$, $F=11.255$, $df=10$; replicate on the right: $P=1.86E-17$, $F=17.621$, $df=10$),
 202 followed by multiple comparisons of means between the C4-expressing lines against the
 203 reference group (35S:GFP), by applying Dunnett's test; asterisks represent statistically

204 significant differences at: ***, $P < 0.001$; ns, not significant. Note that some pictures in (a) are
205 also shown in Figure S10a, as reference, since both experiments were run in parallel.

206 b. Pictures show representative root tip angles in plants expressing C4, C4 Mild, or their
207 respective mutant forms (T3 generation), at 7 dpg, after growing for 12 h rotated 90 degrees
208 with respect to their initial growing position: the new g force direction is depicted in the pictures
209 by the yellow arrow to the left. Scale bar, 1 cm. A stable line expressing GFP (35S:GFP) is
210 shown as reference. Graphs show quantifications of the root tip angles in the previous
211 transgenic plants, after receiving the gravitropic treatment, in two independent experiments.
212 Each dot represents the individual measurement of a root tip angle, and error bars indicate
213 standard deviations. Root tip angles of a minimum of 14 plants were analyzed per line.
214 Differences between groups were assessed by applying Kruskal-Wallis test (replicate on the
215 left: $P = 0.031$, $H = 19.74$, $df = 10$; replicate on the right: $P = 3.046 \cdot 10^{-7}$, $H = 49.67$, $df = 10$), followed
216 by pairwise comparisons between each group and the reference group (35S:GFP) (Mann-
217 Whitney U test, significance 0.005, after Bonferroni's correction for multiple comparisons);
218 asterisks represent statistically significant differences at: ***, $P < 0.001$; **, $P = 0.002$; ns, not
219 significant.

220 C4, C4 from TYLCV; C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild.

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236 **Figure S13. Transcriptomic analyses of C4-expressing Arabidopsis plants.**

237 Transcriptomic analyses were performed in aerial parts of 12-days-old Arabidopsis plants
 238 expressing C4 from TYLCV (C4), C4 from TYLCV-Mild (C4 Mild), or their respective mutant
 239 forms (T3 generation). Three biological replicates, each of them including material of at least
 240 30 plants, were subjected to massive RNA sequencing, and comparative analyses of total
 241 RNAseq data were performed between each mutant line and the reference line (Col-0 WT
 242 plants). The summary of the total RNAseq data can be found in Table S2; counts and RPKM
 243 mapping to the C4 transgene can be found in Table S3.

244 a. Venn diagrams show the total number of genes found as differentially expressed (DEGs,
 245 fold-change=2, FDR<0.05), either downregulated (Venn diagrams on the left) or upregulated
 246 (Venn diagrams on the right) per transgenic line analyzed, as well as the numbers of
 247 overlapping genes found as differentially expressed in both transgenic lines. On the right,
 248 the stacked bar graphs summarize the total number of DEGs, either down- or upregulated, per
 249 line analyzed. Complete lists of DEGs can be found in Table S4.

250 b. Upper panel shows the principal component analysis (PC) graph, with PC1 and PC2
251 explaining 19% and 16%, respectively, of the total variance in the transcriptome data; bottom
252 panel shows heatmap and hierarchical clustering of samples in (a); colour scales indicate Z-
253 scores.

254 c, d. Functional enrichment analyses of downregulated (c) or upregulated (d) DEGs, in the
255 indicated samples: the lists show the first 20 significantly overrepresented Gene Ontology (GO)
256 categories (FDR<0.05) from the Biological Process ontology, after discarding low-level,
257 redundant categories; colour codes and scales represent $-\text{LOG}_{10}\text{FDR}$ values. For a full list of
258 raw GO categories per genotype, see Table S5.

259 e. Enrichment analyses of DEGs (down- or upregulated genes) in The Kyoto Encyclopaedia
260 of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathways: the lists show significantly overrepresented KEGG
261 categories (FDR<0.05). Colour codes and scales represent $-\text{LOG}_{10}\text{FDR}$ values. Full lists of
262 genes and KEGG categories per genotype can be checked in Table S6. Note that no
263 significant KEGG pathways enrichment was found for the upregulated DEGs in 35S:C4
264 genotype.

265 f, Visualization through Pathview of the 'Plant hormone signal transduction' KEGG pathway
266 relative to auxin signaling, when found significantly enriched (FDR<0.05), for downregulated
267 (35S:C4, 35S:C4 Mild and 35S:C4 Mild_m genotypes, highlighted in red color) or upregulated
268 (35S:C4 Mild and 35S:C4_{CCLm2}, highlighted in green color) DEGs.

269 DEGs, differentially expressed genes (here, when compared to WT); DR, downregulated
270 DEGs; UP, upregulated DEGs; C4, C4 from TYLCV; C4 Mild, C4 from TYLCV-Mild; WT, Col-
271 0 WT. Common abbreviations used in GO categories: E., Energy; Reg., Regulation; proc.,
272 process; Neg., Negative; Biol., Biological; int., interactions; betw., between; org., organisms;
273 Pos., Positive.

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276 **Figure S14. C4 from TYLCV does not affect responses to exogenously applied IAA nor**
 277 **accumulation of IAA in transgenic Arabidopsis plants.**

278 a, b. C4-expressing plants (T3 generation) were grown in vertical plates supplemented with
 279 increasing concentrations of IAA (0-40 nM) and, at 12 days post-germination, primary root
 280 length (a) as well as the number of lateral roots per cm of primary root (b) were determined by
 281 Image J. In the graph, each dot represents the average, and the error bars the standard
 282 deviations; a minimum of ten roots were analyzed per line, and the experiment was repeated
 283 two times with similar results.

284 c. IAA content in 11-day-old whole seedlings of transgenic plants expressing C4 or its mutant
 285 forms C4_{CCLm1} and C4_{CCLm2}. As controls, WT plants as well as the IAA over-accumulating
 286 mutant *sur1* were included. In the graph, each dot represents the IAA content of one biological
 287 replicate. The horizontal line represents the average IAA content, and the error bars the
 288 standard deviations. Significant differences between groups were determined by one-way
 289 ANOVA ($P=0.0022$, $F=5.542$, $df=7$), followed by multiple comparisons of means between the
 290 C4-expressing lines and the over-accumulating line *sur1* against the reference group (WT),
 291 by applying Dunnett's test; asterisks represent statistically significant differences at: **, $P<0.01$;
 292 ns, not significant.

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295 **Figure S15. BFA (Brefeldin A)-treated Arabidopsis seedlings show developmental**
 296 **alterations reminiscent of those induced by transgenic expression of C4 from TYLCV.**

297 a. 5-day-old wild-type (WT) Arabidopsis plants were transferred to ½ MS vertical plates
 298 supplemented with different concentrations of BFA (1, 10, or 25 μ M dissolved in DMSO) or
 299 DMSO (control) for 7 days; pictures were taken at 12 days post-germination (dpg). On the left,
 300 pictures show root growth; note that BFA treatment induced the appearance of C4-like root
 301 phenotypes, characterized by wider lateral root angles (depicted with yellow arrows at 1 μ M),
 302 aberrant root tip angles (depicted with white arrows at 10 μ M), or curly rosette leaves (detailed
 303 pictures on the right).

304 b. Similar experiments as the ones described above were carried out with Arabidopsis plants
 305 expressing C4 or its mutant forms C4_{CCLm1} and C4_{CCLm2} (T3 generation), in the presence of 25
 306 μ M BFA. Representative phenotypes of roots (on the left) and rosettes (on the right) are
 307 presented. Red lines in both (a) and (b) mark the root size before BFA treatment, as reference.
 308 Scale bar, 1 cm. BFA, Brefeldin A; C4, C4 from TYLCV.

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310 **Figure S16. C4_{CCLm3} does not interact with RLD proteins nor recruit them to the plasma**
 311 **membrane.**

312 a. Interaction between C4_{CCLm3} and full-length Arabidopsis RLD1-4 or their BRX domain
 313 (BRXD), tested by yeast two-hybrid (Y2H).

314 b. Subcellular localization of Arabidopsis RFP-RLD1-4 transiently expressed in *N.*
 315 *benthamiana* leaves in the presence or absence of C4_{CCLm3}-GFP. Images were taken at 2 days
 316 post-agroinfiltration (dpa).

317 c. Subcellular localization of C4-GFP/C4_{CCLm3}-GFP upon transient expression in *N.*
 318 *benthamiana* leaves. Aniline blue labels callose deposits. Arrowheads indicate
 319 plasmodesmata. Images were taken at 2 dpa.

320 BF, bright field. Z-stack shows the maximum projection of a vertical cross-section through the
 321 observed cells. Scale bar, 20 μ m. All experiments in this figure were performed three time with
 322 similar results; one representative replicate is shown here.

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341 d. Representative phenotypes of *N. benthamiana* plants infected with TYLCV or TYLCV^{C4_{CCLm3}}
342 at 21 days post-inoculation (dpi). In upper panels, lateral and zenithal images of whole plants
343 are presented; bottom panels show typical symptoms of infection in systemic leaves from three
344 different plants. Scale bar, 2 cm.

345 e, f. Viral accumulation was analyzed in *N. benthamiana* plants in both systemic (e) and local
346 (f) infections by qPCR, at 21 dpi (e) or 2 dpi (f). Violin plots show the aggregate results obtained
347 in 5 independent trials, where each dot represents one biological replicate consisting of an
348 individual plant, the thick lines represent median values, and thin lines the lower/upper
349 quartiles. A minimum of 5 plants were analyzed per infection and trial, when possible.
350 Differences between TYLCV and TYLCV^{C4_{CCLm3}} were assessed by applying Mann-Whitney U
351 test (*, $P=0.042$; ns, not significant). TYLCV^{C4₁₋₈}, a mutant virus carrying a premature stop
352 codon mutation in the C4 sequence resulting in the translation of the first 8 aa only (Rosas-
353 Diaz *et al.* 2018), was included in (d), (e) and (f) as reference; EV, Empty vector; R indicates
354 each of the independent replicates.

355 The experiments in (a) and (b) were performed two times with similar results. The experiments
356 in (c) were performed three times with similar results. One replicate is shown here.

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Figure S18. Whitefly choice assay: viral accumulation and experimental design.

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a. Accumulation of TYLCV and its mutant form TYLCV^{C4CCLm3} in the tomato plants used for the dual choice assays with *Bemisia tabaci* (whitefly) in Fig. 4e. Systemic samples were collected at 19 days post-inoculation. The violin plot shows the aggregate results obtained in three independent replicates; each dot represents viral accumulation per individual plant, thick line the median, and thin lines the lower/upper quartiles. Statistically significant differences were assessed by applying Mann-Whitney U test; ns, not significant. R indicates each of the independent replicates.

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b. Experimental design followed in dual choice assays with whiteflies and tomato plants infected with TYLCV or TYLCV^{C4CCLm3}, as described in Ontiveros *et al.*, 2022. TYLCV- and TYLCV^{C4CCLm3}-infected leaflets were placed in the corners of a cage occupying alternate positions (2x2), surrounding the flight release platform situated in the middle, where an individual whitefly was placed and its preference recorded. Choice assays were repeated individually at least 60 times per experiment (60 individual whiteflies, i.e. 60 biological replicates).

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